

INTERNET OF THINGS BASED SMART HELMET FOR ALERTING ACCIDENT

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Abstract

This article is about a smart helmet, a novel idea that increases the safety of motorcycle riding. In order to stop vehicles from starting while the driver is not wearing a helmet, this technique was developed. or is inebriated. Furthermore, with the help of a GPS GSM-based tracking system, it detects accidents and sends SMS notifications to particular persons showing the bike's location and speed just before the collision, assisting ambulances in arriving at the precise spot. We want to integrate all of the sensors into the helmet, which will wirelessly transmit data to the module attached to the bike engine. There will be two modules in this smart motorcycle helmet system with one helmet and one motorcycle. The bike module has a vibration sensor, GPS, and GSM, whilst the helmet module has an alcohol sensor, a helmet sensor, and a switch. Both of these modules connect wirelessly using an Arduino as a microcontroller and an RF transmitter and receiver with encoder and decoder.

Keywords: Helmet, GSM module, GPS module, Sensors, SMS, RF Tx and Rx

INTRODUCTION

The smart helmet is presented in the suggested project work, and it ensures that the rider needs it to start the bike. The bike won't start until the key and the helmet are both present because this helmet uses a straightforward cable replacement for wirelessly turning on a bike. Additionally, whenever the ignition is turned on, the alcohol sensor checks the level of alcohol in the driver's breath and, if necessary, switches the motorcycle off. he is inebriated. GSM and GPS technology are utilised to make driving safer.

Vibration sensors are attached to a microcontroller board and positioned in various spots on the helmet where there is a higher chance of being hit. These sensors detect when the rider crashes and the helmet strikes the ground and communicate the information to the microcontroller board, which then uses the associated GPS module to retrieve the GPS data.

A message is sent to an ambulance or family members via the GSM module when the data reaches a particular degree of stress. In road traffic incidents around the world, more than 1.3 million people are killed and 20–50 million more suffer injuries each year. According to the 2013 Global Status Report on Road Safety, 1.24 million people die in traffic accidents each year, which is still too many..

Only 28 countries, accounting for 7% of the global population, have full road safety rules in place for five important risk factors: drunk driving, going too fast, and failing to use child restraints, seatbelts, or motorcycle helmets. A smart helmet has been created as a solution to this problem, helping to decrease the number of accidents that occur each day as well as the death rate. Many individuals die in nations where motorcycles are more common, such as India, because they do not wear motorcycle helmets.

Despite repeated government warnings about the need of wearing a helmet and wearing a seat belt, the majority of drivers ignore them. The majority of People don't wear traditional helmets for safety; rather, they do so to avoid getting tickets from traffic enforcement agents. reasons. As a result, these helmets do not ensure the driver's safety.

Helmets serve as a basic form of protection for two-wheeler riders. It does not, however, ensure that the rider adheres to all traffic laws. As a result, the smart helmet can be used to solve this problem.

Objectives

The major goal of this technology is to create a helmet that protects motor cycle riders while also preventing occurrences of drunk driving. It identifies whether the cyclist has been in an accident, and if he has, it notifies the guardian and sends an SMS.

Proposed system

We're developing a smart helmet with internet of things (IoT) technologies to ensure bikers' safety.

- The system detects whether the rider is wearing a helmet or not; if he is, the car will only start if he is. This prevents motorcycle accidents on the road.
- If the bike rider is engaged in a collision, the device recognises it and notifies the registered contact with a location.
- It detects how much alcohol the rider has consumed; if the rider has drank too much alcohol, the bike engine will not start.

We are utilising IoT technology, which offers cutting-edge methods for warning the rider and guaranteeing that the rider is paying attention, for the safety of the bike rider regulations. The most fundamental kind of protection for anyone riding two wheels is a helmet, which is a must for everyone who rides a bike or a motorbike.

It does not guarantee the rider's safety, though, and the rider will not abide by traffic regulations. To avoid receiving a challan from the traffic police, the majority of people wear standard helmets, yet these helmets do not safeguard the driver's safety. We must thus use the smart helmet to address these problems.

Implementation

Table 1: Hardware components

Arduino Uno Board
Arduino Nano Board
GSM SIM 800
GPS Neo 6M 0001
Alcohol Sensor MQ-3
16*2 Matrix Display
Accelerometer ADXL345
RF transmitter- Receiver module
Antenna
Push Buttons
5v Voltage Regulator
Capacitor(1uF)
Potentiometers(4k7)
BergSticks
Connecting Wires
PCB

Microcontroller: In this paper, a microcontroller called the ATMEGA 328p is used. It could be thought of as the brain of the circuit. It is possible to save the commands and values that are used during the operation of the circuit. Before being delivered to other devices, the microcontroller processes each signal.

GPS Module: A satellite-based navigation system called the Global Positioning System (GPS) can be used to determine the precise location of an accident. It recognises and transmits to the GSM module the Longitude and Latitude values of a particular place.

GSM Modem SIM800: GSM, or Global System for Mobile Communication, is an acronym. A link between a computer and a GSM network is established using it. There are included common interfaces like RS232, USB, and others. Using the SIM card, it is utilised to deliver SMS messages.

Vibration Sensor: Vibration sensors in helmets are devices that measure, display, and analyse linear velocity, displacement, proximity, and acceleration.

Gas Sensor (MQ3): This sensor detects the presence of alcohol in a biker's breath. It is powered by a 23.3V electrical supply. The driver cannot operate the motorcycle if the sensitivity of MQ-3 in the breath is greater than 0.04 mg/L.

Software description:

ARDUINO IDE: The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a cross-platform software programme for Windows, macOS, and Linux that was created in C and C++. With the aid of third-party cores, it is used to create and upload programmes to Arduino-compatible boards as well as other vendor development boards.

Working

The system has two sections Helmet section and Bike section

Helmet system

Fig 1: Helmet block diagram

Because the circuit's supply voltage can be changed at any time. To assure the circuit's safety, the battery outputs are connected to the LM7805 '5 volt' voltage regulator. The output from the regulator is fed to the MQ3 gas sensor and the Arduino NANO microcontroller board, which contains the ATMEGA32a IC, which serves as the circuit's brain, and the same supply voltage of 5v is fed to the Radio Frequency transmitter module, which includes a soldered ENCODER IC (HT12E).

As we know, the UNO does not switch on the RF module when the gas sensor is triggered by alcohol consumption. If no triggering occurs, the UNO activates the RF module, causing the encoded bit value to be sent to the receiver section.

The same logic applies to the pushbutton, where if the rider's head does not compress the mechanical spring switch, no bits are transmitted by the RF module. If the data is compressed, the operation runs smoothly and without interruption. The helmet module is ready to transmit a message to the bike module indicating that the rider is wearing a helmet, which will be displayed on the 'Liquid Crystal Display.' Engine ignition will be turned on only if the Helmet Module sends both bit values of "high," which is value one.

Bike system

Fig 2: Bike system block diagram

The receiver module for radio frequencies simply receives signals with logic values of 1. The incoming Bits are DECODED using HD12D, which then triggers the ARDUINO UNO microcontroller, which checks for loops. If the loop is completed, the bike will turn on immediately. If the loop fails, that is, when the bit value of 0 zero is received, the bike does not switch on. Coming to the second loop condition of the Bike Module, if the rider has an accident while riding, the ADXL345 accelerometer will be triggered, causing the microcontroller UNO to loop, and if 'YES', the microcontroller will turn on the GPS module global positioning system, which will assist the Guardian or nearest police station in locating the accident spot. During the programme, the SIM subscriber identity module number will be added to the microcontroller. This data is communicated through a GSM module, which is a global system for mobile phones that includes a SIM card. The messages will be shown on the LCD 16*2 display once they have been dispatched.

RESULT

IoT-based two-wheeler safety technology called Smart Helmet is incredibly dependable and safe. This system's main objective is to shield anyone wearing the helmet from harm in the case of an accident. It stops people from driving after drinking. The outcomes can pinpoint an accident and notify the registered contacts with a 90% accuracy of the location, enabling the guardians to learn about the person's condition and administer the necessary medical care. To identify an accident, the results of tilting a helmet are compared to the threshold value and the helmet fall value. If the rider is too drunk, the bike won't start since the technology detects the presence of alcohol in the rider's breath.

CONCLUSION

We assessed the following work in this project:

The overall safety needs for a human on a daily basis while using a wheeled motor vehicle such as a motorcycle that they ride primarily on roads.

Also, the importance of wearing riding gears during the transportation from one place to another. Hence, this project is very handy and useful for automobile applications and also by reducing the number of accidents that may occur through the SOS indication to the driver.

Future scope

There were a few instances where we didn't go into detail. They are as follows: Auto-recharging of the transmitter circuit's battery and Helmet lock-down system that is wireless

References

- 1) 2020 International Conference on Computing and Information Technology, University of Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Volume: 01, Issue: ICCIT- 1441, Page No.: 31 - 34, 9th & 10th Sep. 2020.
- 2) 2018 3rd IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT-2018), MAY 18th & 19th 2018. [3]. International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing, April 4-6, 2019, India. Design of Smart Helmet for Accident Avoidance Jesudoss A, Vybhavi R and Anusha B.
- 3) H. Girish, T. G. Manjunat and A. C. Vikramathithan, "Detection and Alerting Animals in Forest using Artificial Intelligence and IoT," 2022 IEEE Fourth International Conference on Advances in Electronics, Computers and Communications (ICAIECC), 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICAIECC54045.2022.9716679.
- 4) A. Devipriya, H. Girish, V. Srinivas, N. Adi Reddy and D. Rajkiran, "RTL Design and Logic Synthesis of Traffic Light Controller for 45nm Technology," 2022 3rd International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET), 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/INCET54531.2022.9824833.
- 5) S. Vaddadi, V. Srinivas, N. A. Reddy, G. H. R. D and A. Devipriya, "Factory Inventory Automation using Industry 4.0 Technologies," 2022 IEEE IAS Global Conference on Emerging Technologies (GlobConET), 2022, pp. 734-738, doi: 10.1109/GlobConET53749.2022.9872416.
- 6) T G Manjunath , A C Vikramathithan , H Girish, "Analysis of Total Harmonic Distortion and implementation of Inverter Fault Diagnosis using Artificial Neural Network", Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 2161, 1st International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Computational Electronics and Communication System (AICECS 2021) 28-30 October 2021, Manipal, India. <https://iopscience.iop.org/issue/1742-6596/2161/1>

- 7) GIRISH H , “Internet of Things Based Heart Beat Rate Monitoring System”, © September 2022 | IJIRT | Volume 6 Issue 4 | ISSN: 2349-6002 IJIRT 156592 International Journal Of Innovative Research In Technology 227
- 8) Dr Girish H, Dr. Mangala Gowri , Dr. Keshava Murthy , Chetan Naik J, Autonomous Car Using Deep Learning and Open CV, PAGE NO: 107-115, Volume 8 Issue 10 2022, Gradiva review journal, Issn No : 0363-8057, DOI:10.37897.GRJ.2022.V8I8.22.50332
- 9) Girish H. "Intelligent Traffic Tracking System Using Wi-Fi ." International Journal for Scientific Research and Development 8.12 (2021): 86-90.
- 10) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “Emission monitoring system using IOT”, Dogo Rangsang Research Journal, UGC Care Group I Journal, ISSN: 347-7180, Vol – 8 Issue-14, No.6, 2020.
- 11) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “Display and misson computer software loading”, International journal of engineering research & Technology (IJERT), ISSN: 2278-0181, Vol – 10 Issue-08, No.13, August 2020.
- 12) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “A Novel Optimization Framework for Controlling Stabilization Issue in Design Principle of FinFET based SRAM”, International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE) Vol. 9, No. 5 October 2019, pp. 4027~4034. ISSN: 2088-8708, DOI: 10.11591/ijece.v9i5.pp.4027-4034
- 13) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “PAOD: a predictive approach for optimization of design in FinFET/SRAM”, International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE) Vol. 9, No. 2, April 2019, pp. 960~966. ISSN: 2088-8708, DOI: 10.11591/ijece.v9i2.pp.960-966
- 14) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “SOPA: Search Optimization Based Predictive Approach for Design Optimization in FinFET/SRAM”, © Springer International Publishing AG, part of Springer Nature 2019 Silhavy (Ed.): CSOC 2018, AISC 764, pp. 21–29, 2019. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-91189-2_3.
- 15) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “Cost-Effective Computational Modelling of Fault Tolerant Optimization of FinFET-based SRAM Cells”, © Springer International Publishing AG 2017 R. Silhavy et al. (eds.), Cybernetics and Mathematics Applications in Intelligent Systems, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing 574, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-57264-2_1.
- 16) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “A Survey on the Performance Analysis of FinFET SRAM Cells for Different Technologies”, International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT) ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-4 Issue-6, 2016.
- 17) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, “Insights of Performance Enhancement Techniques on FinFET-based SRAM Cells”, Communications on Applied Electronics (CAE) – ISSN: 2394-4714, Foundation of Computer Science FCS, New York, USA .Volume 5 – No.6, July 2016 – www.caeaccess.org

- 18) Girish H, Shashikumar D R, "DESIGN OF FINFET", International Journal of Engineering Research ISSN: 2319-6890) (online), 2347-5013(print) Volume No.5 Issue: Special 5, pp: 992-1128, doi: 10.17950/ijer/v5i5/013 2016.
- 19) Analysis of Smart helmets and Designing an IoT based smart helmet: A cost effective solution for Riders by Divyasudha N, Arulmozhivarman P School of Electrical Engineering VIT University, Vellore Tamil Nadu, India- 632014 Rajkumar E.R Senior Architect at Robert Bosch engineering and solutions Bengaluru, Karnataka, India- 560103.
- 20) World Health Organisation, "Global status report on road safety 2018," 2018
- 21) Nitin Agarwal, Anshul Kumar Singh, Pushpender Pratap Singh Rajesh Sahan. "SMART HELMET, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology. Volume 2, issue 2, May 2015.
- 22) Professor Chitte P.P, Salunke Akshay S. Tharat Aniruddha, N Bhosale, "Smart Helmet & Intelligent Bike System". International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) Volume 03 issue: 05, May-2016.
- 23) Shoeb Ahmed Shabbeer. Merin Meleet Smart helmet for accident detection and notification 2nd IEEE International conference on computational systems and information technology 201.
- 24) Dr. Mangala Gowri S G, Dr. Shashidhar T M, Dr. Sunitha R, Shylaja V, Dr. Girish H, "Design OF 3-BIT CMOS Wallace Multiplier" , Seybold report, ISSN 1533-9211, Volume 18, Page No: 1260-1271 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8300481
- 25) Dr. Mangala Gowri S G, Dr. Girish H, Ramesh N, Dr. Nataraj Vijaypur, "IOT based plant monitoring system and smart irrigation using new features" ResMilitaris, vol.13, n°2, January Issue 2023 <https://resmilitaris.net/menu-script/index.php/resmilitaris/article/view/3312/2608>
- 26) Girish H.2023, Smart Theft Securityvehicular System Using Iot. Int J Recent Sci Res. 14(02), pp. 2881-2884. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24327/ijrsr.2023.1402.0591>
<https://www.recentscientific.com/smart-theft-securityvehicular-system-using-iot>
- 27) Dr. Mangala Gowri S G, Dr. Girish H, Dr. Santosh Dattatray Bhopale, Weed Detection based on Neural Networks, International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), ISSN: 2455-6211 Volume 11, Issue 3, March-2023, Impact Factor: 7.429, Available online at: www.ijaresm.com DOI: <https://doi.org/11.56025/IJARESM.2023.11323351>
- 28) Shashidhara, K.S., Girish, H., Parameshwara, M.C., Rai, B.K., Dakulagi, V. (2023). A Novel Approach for Identification of Healthy and Unhealthy Leaves Using Scale Invariant Feature Transform and Shading Histogram-PCA Techniques. In: Shetty, N.R., Patnaik, L.M., Prasad, N.H. (eds) Emerging Research in Computing, Information, Communication and Applications. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, vol 928. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5482-5_47